

COMMUNICATIVE FEATURES OF SOCIAL DEIXIS.

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about communicative features of social deixis and the importance of using social deixis in the linguistic analysis of the elements of the politeness category. Also, it analyzes communicative importance of social deixis through the example taken from Oscar Wild's play „An Ideal Husband”.

The use of social deixis is important in the linguistic analysis of the elements of the politeness category used by people in the process of mutual communication in society. First off all, we should give definition the term for social deixis itself. Social deixis is reference to the social characteristics or distinctions between, the participants or referents in a speech event. We know from the analysis of linguistic scenarios that each person can perform different roles in different communication situations, depending on the situation. For example, there is a leader in the workplace, a patient who follows the doctor's instructions when he is sick, a good child of his parents or a loving father of his children, a hospitable family head in the family. The interaction of people who play different roles in the process of communication in society is governed by role expectations. In this case, whether a person wants it or not, those around him expect him to behave and behave in accordance with certain patterns

and norms established in society. If the role is not performed well, it is evaluated by the public and more or less restrictions are made depending on the situation. So, communication processes among people in the society take place in different forms and situations according to their social origin, position in society, profession and position. In such communication processes, its participants use elements of politeness in various forms and content to organize the communication process.

Through the following example taken from Oscar Wild's play „An Ideal Husband”, we will show how written communication, which is considered a unique form of communication between people, is organized according to the social status, profession, and position of the participants of the interaction, and how the elements of the category of politeness are uniquely communicative in it. Let's look at the features of it:

SIR ROBERT CHILTERN. [Entering.] Your carriage is here. (act I p 46)

MRS. CHEVELEY. Thanks! Good evening,
Lady Chiltern! Good-night. (act I
p 46)

Lord Goring! I am at Claridge's. Don't you
think you might leave a card. (act I
p 46)

In all these examples, Sir, Mrs and Lord are
considered as social deixis since
they refer to the social role of the
characters.

They express their role in society not their
social relationship. Using this kind of
deixis, has special function which is
expressing the social differences of the
characters and showing their social
relationship among characters.

We can see other category of politeness in
these examples, also:

1. "Yes my dear, I hurried back because I
was worry about my love. Did your father
come to see you?" ("Sharazat "drama script)

2. Well, sir, I guess I am just going as fast as
I can.

In this conversation, the word "sir" is used
to show respect for strangers.

We can see from the above examples that
in the process of communication, the
participants do not only exchange
information, but also influence each other
to achieve their goals. In the process of
communication, communication
participants influence each other during
the exchange of information. To determine
the characteristics of interaction, it is
necessary to study the interactive side of
the communication process. The
interactive side of the communication
process is the mutual influence of the

participants in the organization and
implementation of joint activities. Through
communication, people organize common
activities together. At this point, it should
be emphasized that, taking into account
factors such as the position of people in
society, profession, position, when
organizing the communication process,
elements of politeness specific to each of
them are used.

From the examples given above, we can
conclude that it is a communicative
necessity to pay attention to aspects such
as the social status, profession, position,
and title of the participants in the
communication process and to use the
appropriate elements of politeness.
Because people play different roles in
society in different situations, for example,
they can play the roles of father and
mother at home, friend on the street, boss
and colleague at work. Taking these
circumstances into account, the
organization of the communication process
and the use of appropriate politeness
elements require great skill from the
speaker. Because the proper and
reasonable use of the elements of the
politeness category is considered
important in achieving the general and
private goals of the communication
process. In the process of communication,
the participants do not only exchange
information, but also try to influence each
other and achieve their goals through this
influence. For this process to be successful,
it is important to use the elements of
politeness correctly and in their place.

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